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POST-NEW START STRATEGIC STABILITY: PREDICTABILITY, TRANSPARENCY, AND RESTRAINT

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Abstract

The New Strategic Arms Reduction Treaty (New START) ended on February 5th, 2026, which raises critical questions about the future of nuclear weapons control and strategic stability. This analysis provides a review of New START through the lens of three stabilising functions – predictability, transparency, and restraint – and demonstrates how the treaty has mitigated worst-case war planning, reduced uncertainty, and decreased the incentive for competitive behaviour between the United States and Russia. In addition, the article examines the limitations of these functions, including partial scope, vulnerability to political crises, and inability to deal with the emergence of new technologies and other non-strategic nuclear forces. Using a functional review as a base, the paper analyses the future of strategic stability in a post-New START world and highlights which functions have the possibility of continuing and which functions are most at risk. The findings suggest that while predictability may endure in a weakened form, transparency and restraint are unlikely to survive without formal mechanisms, emphasising the need for flexible, function-specific approaches to nuclear risk management. By shifting the focus from treaty mechanics to stabilising functions, this study offers a novel framework for understanding the dynamics of strategic stability in a more complex and contested nuclear order.

Keywords: New START, Strategic Stability, Nuclear Arms Control, Post-Treaty Risk Management.

Introduction

The expiration of the New Strategic Arms Reduction Treaty (New START - officially the Treaty between the United States and the Russian Federation on Measures for the Further Reduction and Limitation of Strategic Offensive Arms) on 5 February 2026 marked a critical turning point for global nuclear arms control and international security. The last remaining bilateral agreement established legally binding limits on the number of deployed strategic warheads and delivery systems, as well as a framework for transparency and predictability between the world's two largest nuclear powers. New START had also provided legally binding limits on the development and deployment of nuclear weapons. The expiration, for the first time since the early 1970s, removed the constraints of any formal arms control regime from the American - Russian strategic nuclear forces.

The timing of New START's expiration significantly increased its importance given the extreme geopolitical deterioration, resulting from the war in Ukraine, the suspension of all dialogue regarding arms control, and the erosion of verification practices. Because New START did not serve only as a technical instrument to limit the size of nuclear arsenals, but also served as a stabilising mechanism, influencing expectations, reducing uncertainty, and limiting the risks of escalation, primarily through the establishment of limits on worst-case planning and misperceptions. Therefore, the expiration of the treaty has once again sparked controversy surrounding the future of nuclear arms

control, specifically about the possible erosion of predictability, transparency, and restraint: the fundamental elements underpinning strategic stability. With the removal of the legal limits and transparency requirements of New START, both sides can increase the numbers of their deployed strategic nuclear forces, thereby increasing the potential for arms races, crisis instability, and strategic miscalculations.

This article argues that the importance of New START stems not so much from the quantitative limits of the treaty, but from the stabilising functions provided within the strategic relationship of the United States and Russia. "Stabilising functions" refer to those mechanisms through which arms control agreements reduce the potential for nuclear competition, crisis escalation, and strategic miscalculation. These functions operate by establishing certain behaviours, expectations, and planning assumptions among states, rather than simply limiting numerical capabilities.

By institutionalising predictability, transparency, and restraint, New START minimised uncertainty and limited the potential for escalation even when faced with political confrontation. Nevertheless, these stabilising functions were partial, and increasingly fragile; constrained by the limited scope of the treaty, its vulnerability to crises, and inability to account for the proliferation of emerging technologies and broader nuclear dynamics. Based on the function-based analytical approach, this article evaluates the role of New START in maintaining strategic stability and assesses the degree to which its stabilising effects will remain present in the

post-New START period. The central research question of this article – to what extent can the stabilising functions traditionally provided by bilateral arms control be maintained in the absence of New START? – necessitates an analytical model that transcends treaty compliance or continuity and emphasises the underlying mechanisms through which arms control influences state behaviour. Thus, a function-based methodology is particularly suitable to identify both continuities and discontinuities in strategic stability during periods of institutional breakdown.

Research methodology

The theoretical foundation of this analytical model is rooted in strategic stability theory which conceptualises stability as a condition in which the incentives for the initial use of force, arms racing, and crisis escalation are reduced due to a combination of material capabilities, information clarity, and behavioural constraints (Freedman, 2003). Unlike previous approaches that have treated arms control agreements as inherently stabilising, this approach disaggregates stability into three analytically distinct yet interdependent stabilising functions: predictability, transparency, and restraint. Each function corresponds to one of the specific theoretical mechanisms outlined in the deterrence, security dilemma, and institutionalist literature, thus enabling a systematic evaluation of how stability is created and potentially degraded over time.

Predictability is rooted in classical deterrence theory and concepts of crisis and arms race stability. According to Schelling and Halperin, stable deterrence depends not only on capabilities, but also on the ability of adversaries to be able to anticipate what those threats will be (Schelling & Halperin, 1961). Therefore, predictability, through reducing incentives for “worst case” planning by providing information regarding the number, composition, and development of offensive forces, assists in the building of a sense of confidence in one’s capability to carry out a second strike. For the purposes of this analysis, predictability is defined by numerical ceilings, deployment guidelines, and notice requirements that allow for long term strategic planning. Consequently, the assessment of predictability after New START will involve determining whether the use of non-binding alternatives (such as unilateral announcements, existing force structures, or continued operation patterns), can serve as adequate substitutes for legally binding limits.

Transparency draws heavily on security dilemma theory and signalling theory, notably the works of Jervis and others that emphasise the likelihood that uncertain and/or misinterpreted adversary actions may lead to destabilising action–reaction dynamics even among countries committed to the status quo (Jervis, 1978). The transparency mechanisms of arms control (data exchanges, inspection, and notifications) function as a costly signal that restricts deception and reduces ambiguity surrounding both the capabilities and intentions of actors. As such, strategic stability theory suggests that transparency is especially critical for crisis stability, as it narrows the scope for misinterpretation during periods of heightened tension (Acton, 2018). In this context, the article assesses how the erosion of formal

verification under New START affects informational symmetry and whether informal or unilateral transparency measures could reasonably serve as a replacement for institutionalised verification practices.

Restraint is linked to institutionalist and arms racing theories, which emphasise the role of formal rules in shaping long-term competitive behaviour. Authors like Glaser and Morgan suggest that unregulated strategic competition will typically generate self-sustaining arms racing dynamics based on hedging, uncertainty and “worst case” assumptions (Glaser, 2010). Arms control serves to maintain arms racing stability through the imposition of ceilings and qualitative limits that lower incentives for competitive growth in offensive forces and indicate an acceptance of sufficiency versus dominance. In addition to quantitative limitations, restraint is analysed as a behavioural norm reinforced by third-party constraints. The function-based approach allows for an evaluation of whether restraint can continue through unilateral self-restraint or normative expectations once legally binding obligations expire.

In terms of methodology, the function-based approach enables a comparative examination of two temporal conditions, namely, the period under New START, and the post-New START environment. Treaty texts, official statements, compliance reports and analyses by experts are examined to determine how each stabilising function was established institutionally, how each function operated in practice, and at what point they became subject to political disruption. This framework does not treat treaty expiration as a binary event but rather permits a nuanced assessment of the degree to which each function continues to exist (function persistence), deteriorate (function degradation) or evolve (function transformation).

Importantly, this methodology directly addresses the research question by converting the analytical focus from the continued existence of the treaty to the continued existence of its stabilising effects. Strategic stability theory indicates that stability can continue in either weakened or informal forms when some mechanism remains viable, regardless of whether there exists a formal agreement. Transparency reduces asymmetries and misperception, predictability constrains reactive escalation, and restraint limits competitive pressure. All three of these functions, by reducing the risk of unintended and/or accidental escalation, serve to support the continuation of stability. By framing these mechanisms as stabilising functions, the paper demonstrates both the theoretical and practical significance of arms control agreements, as well as illustrates how treaties create stability through regulated interaction and behavioural constraints, rather than merely through legally established ceilings. Furthermore, this approach enables the identification of which elements of stability are most resilient, which are most dependent on institutionalisation, and where the greatest risks of destabilisation are likely to emerge in the post–New START era. Through bridging theoretical debate concerning strategic stability with practical policy analysis, the function-based framework provides a structured and theoretically

grounded method of assessing nuclear risk management in an increasingly restrictive arms control environment.

Features of New START

New START is an example of a post-Cold War attempt to create legally binding nuclear disarmament between the United States and Russia. The New Strategic Arms Reduction Treaty (New START) was signed in Prague in April 2010, entered into force in February 2011, and replaced the 1991 Strategic Arms Reduction Treaty (START I) that expired in December 2009 (U.S. Department of State, 2024). Its negotiation reflected a shared recognition that, despite the end of ideological confrontation, unconstrained strategic nuclear competition would continue to pose significant risks to international security.

New START was a bilateral agreement, subject to ratification in each state's domestic legislation, and based upon international law. Unlike previous arms control treaties, New START did not include a wide range of weapons systems but focused narrowly on deployed strategic offensive nuclear weapons. This limited scope was intended to provide a politically feasible and verifiable framework for monitoring the parties' compliance at a time when trust between the parties was fragile (Liang, 2024).

Initially, New START was concluded for a period of ten years, with the possibility of a single five-year extension. In February 2021, the United States and Russia agreed to exercise this extension, setting the treaty's expiration date on 5 February 2026 (Arms Control Association, 2021). Importantly, New START contains no further extension mechanisms, making its expiration a definitive endpoint.

At the core of New START were quantitative limits on strategic nuclear forces. Article III capped each party at:

- 1,550 deployed strategic nuclear warheads
- 700 deployed intercontinental ballistic missiles (ICBMs), submarine-launched ballistic missiles (SLBMs), and heavy bombers
- 800 deployed and non-deployed launchers in total.

Beyond limiting the numbers of these weapons systems, the New START also created a comprehensive verification and transparency regime. Article XI outlined the core elements of the verification and compliance process and established the use of National Technical Means (NTM) and Cooperative Verification Measures (CVM). Additionally, it included a Bilateral Consultative Commission (BCC) to address any implementation issues that may arise. Finally, Article XI created the legal authority for exchanging information necessary to support transparency and confidence in compliance, prohibited interference with each other's NTM, and the use of concealment methods that could hinder verification, thereby reinforcing mutual confidence in treaty implementation.

Crucially, Article XI linked verification to the treaty's broader transparency regime by authorising on-site inspections, data exchanges, notifications, and exhibitions, which are outlined in detail in the Protocol to

the Treaty. By including verification as a legal requirement, rather than merely as a voluntary activity, Article XI institutionalised transparency as a stabilising factor, reduced uncertainty, deterred non-compliance, and provided each party with sufficient confidence in assessing the size and nature of the other's strategic forces. These mechanisms were designed to detect violations of the treaty, but also to reduce uncertainty and prevent misinterpretation of routine military activities.

In addition to the central limits and verification mechanisms, New START also addressed the sensitive issue of missile defence in a limited but stabilising way. While the treaty imposed no restrictions on either the United States or Russia regarding their respective missile defence programs, its preamble acknowledged the interrelationship between offensive and defensive strategic arms and reaffirmed that existing missile defence systems do not threaten the viability of strategic deterrence. Operationally, Article V prohibited the conversion of ICBM and SLBM launchers into missile defence interceptor launchers and vice versa. This provision prevented the rapid development of new capabilities in response to perceived threats and contributed to the predictability of military planning and budgeting. Although missile defence was not restricted by the limits of the treaty, the provisions related to the use of launchers for both strategic offensive and defensive purposes contribute to strategic stability by reducing uncertainty about launchers roles and future force expansion (Antonov, 2012).

Overall, New START has played a pivotal role in defining the current relationship between the United States and Russia concerning their strategic nuclear capabilities. By imposing legally binding limits on deployed strategic forces, it continued the trajectory of nuclear reductions begun at the end of the Cold War. It also preserved a critical degree of predictability and mutual visibility at a moment when other key pillars of the arms control architecture, most notably the Anti-Ballistic Missile (ABM) and Intermediate-Range Nuclear Forces (INF) treaties, had collapsed. New START's significance therefore extended beyond its numerical ceilings: it institutionalised regular interaction among military and technical experts, reinforced norms of restraint, and provided a stabilising reference point even amid profound political tension. In this way, the treaty functioned not only as a mechanism for limiting strategic arsenals, but also as a confidence-building instrument that helped manage strategic rivalry between the world's two largest nuclear powers.

New START and the Provision of Stabilising Functions

New START has promoted stability, not only through numerical reductions, but by performing a set of stabilising functions that shaped expectations, strategic force planning, and risk perceptions between the United States and the Russian Federation. It has established an expectation of predictability, transparency, and restraint among the two countries by mitigating the incentive for an arms race and the risk of miscalculations that arise from nuclear competition. Evaluating New START through these functions provides a more precise understanding of its stabilising effects than an

exclusive focus on warhead ceilings or compliance records.

Predictability

Predictability was one of New START's greatest contributing factors to stability. Through establishing clear, legally binding limits on deployed strategic warheads and delivery systems, it constrained the range of possible force postures available to both parties. At the time of the February 2018 New START implementation deadline, both the United States and the Russian

Federation had achieved the treaty's central limits (See Figure 1). These limitations reduced the uncertainty about the future size and configuration of their arsenals and allowed both sides to make long term strategic plans based on the assumption of a stable and predictable situation rather than assuming the worst-case scenario (Albertson & Sokov, 2023).

Figure 1. – Nuclear Warhead Limit under New START

Source: <https://www.armscontrol.org/factsheets/new-start-glance>

After 2023, no official New START compliance data is available since Russia suspended its participation in the treaty's verification. For 2024 and 2025, independent analysts provide open-source estimates of the United States and Russian nuclear arsenals, however, these figures account for the total estimated number of nuclear weapons, not simply the treaty-limited deployed strategic warheads, the total inventories include many more warheads in reserve or storage. (Kristensen, Korda, Johns & Knight, 2025). While New START limited deployed strategic warheads to 1,550 per side, the expert reports from the Federation of American Scientists indicate that both parties likely remained close to this limit through 2024 and 2025

According to Nuclear Notebook 2025, the United States had 1770 and 775 deployed warheads and delivery systems last year, while Russia had 1,718 warheads and 592 deployed weapon systems, respectively. However, in the field of tactical nuclear weapons, the Russian Federation had a nuclear capability seven times greater, which is a worrying issue, especially for Europe.

In addition to the numerical limits, predictability was supported by the regular exchanges of data and notifications concerning changes in strategic forces. This process allowed both sides to anticipate routine developments, such as the modernisation or redeployment of forces, without assuming that they were indicative of

hostile intent. New START thus reduced the pressure to rapidly expand or modernise forces in response to perceived hostile actions (Vignard, ed., 2010).

Transparency

Transparency constitutes the second major stabilising function of New START. The treaty's verification mechanism, which included on-site inspections, data exchanges and notification obligations, permitted each side to obtain knowledge of the composition and deployment of the strategic nuclear forces of the other. Transparency accordingly reduced reliance on national technical means alone and lowered the risk of the misinterpretation of military activities (Woolf, 2020). Since the entry into force of the New START Treaty, and up to February 1, 2023, the two parties have conducted (U.S. Department of State):

- 328 on-site inspections,
- 25,449 notifications exchanged,
- 19 meetings of the Bilateral Consultative Commission, and
- 42 biannual data exchanges on strategic offensive arms subject to the treaty.

Through the establishment of a framework for the routine interaction of military and technical personnel, New START normalised the exchange of information between the two sides, regardless of whether there existed mutual trust. The exchanges facilitated a shared

understanding of the respective force structures and operational procedures, thereby enhancing confidence that the military activities observed by the parties were in conformity with the mutually agreed upon boundaries. As such, the transparency mechanisms under New START fulfilled not only a monitoring-compliance function, but also a confidence-building function critical to crisis stability (Patton, Podvig, & Schell, 2013).

The mechanisms of transparency also improved strategic communications by providing clarity to intent. In environments characterised by ambiguity, clarity is critical to mitigate the risk of escalation. The treaty's verification mechanism, therefore, reduced the likelihood that routine modernisation or exercises could be interpreted as preparation for first use or as escalatory coercion.

Restraint

To begin with, New START was a source of strategic stability as it institutionalised restraint in strategic nuclear rivalry. The treaty established legally binding constraints on strategic nuclear weapons; however, it also created a variety of political and reputational disincentives against violation or suspension of compliance. In this regard, the treaty was not only observed by its parties but also conveyed to the public that the parties were committed to share norms of prudent stewardship of their nuclear arsenals. Violation or suspension of compliance would have had serious implications for diplomacy and strategy. Furthermore, the treaty preserved the mutual recognition of strategic parity and shared vulnerability, both of which are essential elements of stable deterrence. Therefore, New START limited the possibilities for strategic advantage through rapid build-up and reduced incentives for destabilising strategies based upon acquiring escalation dominance.

New START clearly allowed for the replacement, upgrade, and modernisation of existing strategic offensive systems, as noted in Article V, so long as the new systems remained below the agreed ceilings and were made subject to transparency and verification measures. By establishing quantitative limits rather than qualitative attributes of strategic systems, New START incorporated restraint into the magnitude of competition rather than the technological content of it. This approach reflected a common view that modernisation is a regular and necessary part of maintaining credible deterrence capabilities and that unregulated increases in numbers pose a greater risk to strategic stability. Thus, modernisation under New START served strategic stability by ensuring forces remain effective and safe while preserving predictability and confidence in mutual restraint (Karakaev, 2023).

Taken together, predictability, transparency, and restraint illustrate how New START functioned as a stabilising instrument beyond its formal legal provisions. Although these functions did not eliminate rivalries or preclude political conflict, they diminished the strategic impact of those rivalries by limiting competitive pressures and reducing uncertainty. However, the extent to which New START's stabilising functions were effective depended on the level of political com-

mitment and favourable security conditions; this represents a significant challenge when evaluating the limitations of the treaty and its eventual expiration date.

NEW START's Limitations in Maintaining Strategic Stability

Although New START provided some stabilising features, it was unable to maintain strategic stability either comprehensively or in face of political and technological changes. A similar functional framework (predictability, transparency, and restraint) reveals that New START's stabilising effects were limited, contingent and weakening. These limits help explain why the expiration of New START created considerable challenges to achieving strategic stability and why the treaty was insufficient as a long-term stabilising mechanism.

Limitations to Predictability

Despite its contribution to strategic predictability, New START imposed limits only on deployed strategic nuclear forces; therefore, many other aspects of nuclear competition remained outside the treaty's scope. Non-deployed warheads, reserve stockpiles, and non-strategic (tactical) nuclear weapons were not included in the treaty, thereby allowing each party to retain sizeable capacities above treaty limitations. This partial coverage reduced the treaty's ability to provide a comprehensive picture of overall nuclear posture and weakened predictability at the margins (Diakov, Miasnikov & Kadyshev, 2011).

New START's failure to address emerging technologies that continue to influence the basis for strategic decision-making further exacerbated limitations to predictability. New START did not account for hypersonic delivery systems, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), new types of strategic platforms, or advanced missile defence systems, all of which increase the complexity associated with assessing survivability and second-strike credibility. As such, as these technologies develop, the assumption that numeric ceilings on traditional delivery systems became less reliable indicators of strategic balance (Erästö, 2021).

As a result, while New START stabilised certain quantitative aspects of strategic forces, it did not restrict the qualitative development of nuclear arsenals, creating an incentive for the parties to engage in planning based on uncertainty regarding future technological trajectories, thereby reintroducing elements of worst-case thinking that the treaty was originally designed to mitigate.

Disruption of Erosion of Transparency

Transparency mechanisms within New START were also susceptible to disruptions in politics and security. On-site inspections were suspended in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic (Gottemoeller, 2022). Resumption of inspections following the pandemic was then impeded by the outbreak of the war in Ukraine in February 2022 (Bugos, 2022). Moreover, Moscow delayed the Bilateral Consultative Commission meeting for political and technical reasons in late 2022, which disrupted both compliance monitoring and discussions regarding advanced strategic nuclear delivery systems. It is worth noting that Russia did not formally withdraw from New START and asserted that it continues to comply with the core limits of the treaty (Ministry of

Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation, 2023). However, the lack of on-site inspections and data exchange diminished the ability to effectively monitor compliance. After 2023, there was no access to officially verified figures on treaty-limited warheads. Information available for 2024–2025 comes from independently assessed expert estimates instead of official compliance data from New START.

The suspension of New START's verification mechanisms highlights the vulnerability of transparency measures to broader geopolitical events and shifts in political will. Russia's suspension of New START's verification mechanisms was framed in terms of the broader strategic environment, with Moscow arguing that U.S. actions threatened its national security and could not be separated from arms control obligations (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation, 2023). This demonstrated that the effectiveness of verification depends on the willingness and continued cooperation of both parties.

The recent interruptions demonstrate that transparency is not solely dependent on technical capability, but on the larger political context, and without consistent cooperation, even legally binding mechanisms may lose much of their value in promoting stabilisation. The interruption of inspection activities reduced the level of trust among parties regardless of whether numerical limits on strategic forces were formally maintained. The interruption of on-site inspections and regular consultation weakened transparency, raised the risk of misperception, and reduced the ability to differentiate between routine changes to military forces and destabilising actions. Additionally, establishing verification mechanisms as part of broader political grievances creates a hazardous precedent by politicising arms control commitments and making them vulnerable to extraneous crises. As a result, the suspension accelerated the erosion of the arms control architecture and diminished New START's capacity to contribute to strategic stability in its final years (Williams, 2023).

Weakening of Restraint

New START's capacity to enforce restraint was similarly limited. The treaty did not limit the development of qualitative advances and more versatile strategic systems within current numeric limitations. Modernisation efforts, framed as replacement rather than expansion, continued to proceed largely unchecked, enabling the development of more capable and diverse strategic systems within existing numerical limits (TACC, 2025).

By the end of 2023, it is estimated that about 95 percent of Russia's nuclear triad consisted of modern weapons and equipment (Интерфакс, 2023). Moscow has also deployed several new systems in addition to ongoing repair/refurbishment of its nuclear triad, including Yars-M intercontinental ballistic missile, the new Avangard (SS-19 Mod 4) hypersonic glide vehicle (HGV), Kh-95 hypersonic air-launched cruise missile or dual-capable weapon systems, most notably the RS-28 Sarmat (SS-29) ICBM, 9M730 Burevestnik (SSC-X-9 Skyfall) intercontinental bomber, Status-6 Poseidon (Kanyon) underwater drone and 3M-22 Tsirkon (SS-NX-33) anti-ship drone (Johns & Mackenzie, 2024). Some of them were even tested in the ongoing Russian-Ukrainian war.

Similarly, the United States has also continued modernisation across all legs of its nuclear triad. On land, the Sentinel program is replacing the aging IC-BMs; while the sea-based component is being upgraded through the construction of the Columbia-class submarines, life-extension programs for the Trident II D5 missiles, and the W93 warhead program which intended to be deployed on US SSBNs by 2040 (Center for Arms Control and Non-Proliferation, 2021). The Air Force is modernising its nuclear bomber fleet and strategic weapons, including upgrades to the Mk21 re-entry vehicles, the W76-1/Mk4A warhead fuse program, and the development of new systems such as the B61-12 gravity bomb and the AGM-181 Long-Range Standoff Weapon, alongside the introduction of the B-21 Raider bomber (Airforce Technology, 2020).

Moreover, restraint under New START was inherently limited by the treaty's narrow scope, which placed quantitative ceilings on deployed strategic offensive arms but imposed no constraints on other nuclear capabilities. In recent years, this limitation has become increasingly salient. The United States has continued to advance missile defence programmes outside the treaty framework, most notably announcing the development of a next generation homeland missile defence architecture (often referred to as the "Golden Dome") intended to counter emerging threats. Missile defence has been regarded as a core component of strategic stability for many years, and Russian strategic thinking has consistently viewed unconstrained U.S. missile defence as a potential challenge to deterrence credibility (Bazylczyk & Freeman, 2025). Russia, for its part, has highlighted the development of novel strategic systems, including the nuclear-powered Burevestnik cruise missile, which some analysts see as a response to U.S. missile defence advances even though the system has been under development since at least 2018 (Starchak, 2026). These developments suggest that while New START imposed restraint on the number of deployed warheads, it did not prevent either party from pursuing qualitative advances and auxiliary capabilities that shape strategic balance. This pattern underscores how restraint under the treaty was partial and increasingly eroded by modernisation dynamics occurring beyond its formal limits.

Beyond the quantitative dimensions of modernisation, the weakening of restraint under New START also found expression in postures and signalling of nuclear behaviour. Since the beginning of the war in Ukraine in early February 2022, Russia has dramatically increased its nuclear rhetoric; carried out high profile nuclear exercises; and issued repeated reminders of its nuclear weapons capabilities in official public declarations (Arndt & Horowitz, 2022). Moscow revised the nuclear strategy in November 2024 authorizing the government to use nuclear weapons even in the event of a serious attack with conventional weapons. Although none of these actions altered the accountable forces under New START, they indicated an unwillingness to restrain behavioural choices, and a greater reliance on nuclear deterrence to exert political influence. These examples of signalling can be viewed as a form of strategic hedging, which allows for the preservation of escalatory options, and the prevention of foreign intervention, in an environment of increasing uncertainty. Therefore, the restraining effect of New START did not weaken only

through unregulated modernisation but also through changing nuclear postures, and declaratory practices that lowered the nuclear threshold, in general, in strategic dialogue.

Finally, restraint was further weakened by the treaty's purely bilateral structure. There were no constraints from third parties, especially from other nuclear-armed countries; therefore, the incentives to maintain long-term restraint decreased, as strategic planning became increasingly based on unconstrained actors outside of the treaty framework (e.g. China). This condition contributed to the view that bilateral limits, although fair, were insufficient in a wider strategic environment.

Over the years, there have been repeated efforts to extend nuclear arms control to include countries beyond the traditional U.S.–Russia bilateral framework. These attempts reflect an increasingly complex and competing multipolar nuclear order. Multilateralising arms control proposals have usually included either a UN Security Council P5 configuration, including the five recognised nuclear-armed countries under the Non-Proliferation Treaty, or a trilateral configuration including the United States, Russia, and China (Ryabkov, 2020). Most recently, U.S. President Donald Trump stated he wanted to begin nuclear arms control discussions with Moscow and Beijing and ultimately cut their defence budget expenditures that are being spent on nuclear (Shalal & Holland, 2025). According to Trump, the necessity for such a strategy lies in the fact that China intends to at least double its nuclear arsenal over the next decade, while Russia is advancing the development of expensive, destabilising delivery technologies. However, China expressed reluctance to participate in multilateral negotiations until Russia and the U.S. significantly decrease their respective stockpiles (Reif & Bugos, 2020). Similarly, Dmitry Peskov, Russian spokesman, stated that no specific negotiations have occurred yet, and it is still unclear when such contacts may take place (Интерфакс, 2025).

Additionally, the uncertainty regarding the future of New START has incentivised states to pursue hedging strategies. Within the context of nuclear arms control, hedging is defined as actions taken by states to preserve or increase future strategic options under conditions of uncertainty, without immediately violating current legal constraints. Instead of openly expanding numbers, hedging generally includes qualitative upgrades, the development of alternative delivery systems, stockpile management practices, or investment in capabilities that would allow for the rapid expansion of military forces if legal or political restraints are eliminated. Thus, hedging represents a loss of confidence in the continued viability of arms control agreements and signals a state's preparation for a less constrained strategic environment. For example, during the last few years of New START, both the United States and Russia engaged in behaviours that were indicative of strategic hedging, which represented a decline in confidence in the long-term viability of the treaty.

As previously described, the limitations of New START indicate that the treaty's stabilising functions were decreasingly able to perform effectively due to ongoing conflicts, technological advancements, and structural shifts in the nuclear environment. As such, while New START did make significant contributions to stability, the limitations identified above demonstrate that the treaty's stabilising functions were increasingly limited by constraints in the areas of politics, technology, and the nuclear environment that limited its durability. *Table 1* summarises the extent to which New START contributed to predictability, transparency, and restraint, while also highlighting the areas in which these functions proved incomplete or fragile. This comparative assessment provides the analytical foundation for evaluating prospects for strategic stability following the treaty's expiration.

New START's Contribution to the Stabilising Functions		
<i>Stabilising Function</i>	<i>How New START Contributed</i>	<i>Where New START Fell Short</i>
<i>Predictability</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legally binding ceilings on deployed strategic warheads and delivery systems; • Regular data exchanges and notifications; • Reduced incentives for worst-case force planning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coverage limited to deployed strategic systems; • Exclusion of non-strategic nuclear weapons and reserve stockpiles; • No regulation of emerging technologies (e.g. hypersonic).
<i>Transparency</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On-site inspections and verification regime; • Institutionalised information exchange beyond national technical means; • Reduced misinterpretation of routine military activities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suspension of inspections during pandemic and political crises; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politicisation of verification procedures; • Transparency weakest precisely under crisis conditions.
<i>Restraint</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal and normative limits on force expansion; • Political and reputational costs for non-compliance; • Reinforcement of strategic parity and mutual vulnerability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No constraints on qualitative modernisation; • Bilateral limits in a broader unconstrained nuclear environment; • Incentives for hedging behaviour as expiration approached.

Source: edited by the authors

Strategic Stability After New START: Prospects for Stabilising Functions Without Formal Constraints

The expiration of New START on February 5th, 2026, marked the first time since the early 1970's that neither the United States nor the Russian Federation have legally binding limits on the number of deployed strategic nuclear weapons. Although the disappearance of formal limits has created widespread concern regarding the possibility of renewed arms races; it should be emphasised that there remains a distinction between the loss of formally agreed upon limitations and the total collapse of strategic stability. Each party continues to maintain their existing force structures, the long-standing doctrine of mutual deterrence, and the numerous systems for commanding and controlling forces that collectively support a predictable and cautious atmosphere. However, the elimination of treaty-based limits creates new uncertainties in the planning horizon, specifically regarding force expansion, reserve stockpiles, and modernization.

Within this context, assessing the prospects for post-New START stability will require an assessment of the underlying stabilising functions (predictability, transparency, and restraint) that the treaty previously performed. An examination of which functions are expected to survive the expiration of the treaty and those that are most susceptible to decline will allow an estimation of the boundaries of strategic stability / instability in the absence of formal bilateral constraints.

As a stabilising function, predictability is likely to be the most resilient element of post-New START strategic stability, although it will likely exist in a partially and conditionally sustainable state. Prior to the expiration of the treaty, the numerical limits and notification requirements in the treaty provided each party with a clear framework for anticipating the quantity and configuration of the other party's deployed strategic nuclear forces. Some degree of predictability may be preserved after the end of treaty by continued existence of current force structures, long-standing deployment patterns, and mutual acceptance of strategic parity. The rationale behind this thinking was exemplified in Russia's unilateral suggestion to continue abiding by the New START's central numerical limits for one additional year following the treaty's expiration, if the United States reciprocates (President of Russia, 2025). Such action would help to ensure that the current force base exists and would thus minimise uncertainty concerning rapid qualitative changes in either party's deployed nuclear forces and support longer term strategic calculations. However, unilateral declarations, public statements related to the size of deployed forces, and continuing operational norms can only provide limited guidance to planners and therefore illustrate the inherently fragile and reversible nature of post-treaty predictability.

The absence of legally binding limits introduces significant uncertainty. Both the United States and Russia currently have the formal authority to increase the size of their deployed strategic nuclear arsenals, to withdraw warheads from reserve stockpiles, and to ac-

celerate modernisation programs without providing advance notice to the other party. The increased ambiguity will lead to growing probability that each party will prepare for the worst-case scenario and thus engage in behaviours designed to hedge against such eventualities (SIPRI 2025), such as maintaining excess reserves and/or developing flexible launch platforms. Thus, while some degree of predictability is likely to remain following the expiration of the treaty, it is likely to be weaker and more conditional in its nature, sufficient to prevent immediate crisis instability, but insufficient to fully anchor long-term strategic decision-making processes.

New START institutionalised transparency by establishing inspection regimes, data exchanges, and notification procedures. Transparency is likely to be the most vulnerable stabilising function following the expiration of the treaty. National Technical Means, such as satellite monitoring and signal intelligence, will undoubtedly provide some level of insight into the current disposition of forces of the opposing party; however, they are unlikely to provide the same depth and credibility of verification as treaty-based verification (Gleason & Riesbeck, 2020). On-site inspections, telemetry exchanges, and routine notifications provided both parties with objective evidence of compliance, as well as reinforced the mutual confidence that routine military actions were not indicative of hostile intent. Absent these mechanisms, both parties will experience increased uncertainty regarding the operational readiness of the opposing party, the pace of their force modernisation efforts, and the composition and size of the reserve stockpiles (Morić & Korda, 2025).

The vulnerability of transparency is most apparent when political tensions are high, or during times of military tension. Under the experience of the New START Treaty, we have seen that verification systems can be suspended or become politically charged, and without a formal treaty, informally established systems will be even less durable. During crisis situations, unverified information can lead to the amplification of "worst case" thinking and therefore increase the potential for error and unintended escalation. While some form of transparency may still exist, albeit in a limited, ad-hoc manner, transparency's role in the post-treaty period is unlikely to provide the same stabilising effects that existed prior to the treaty's expiration. From a practical perspective, the loss of transparency creates a significant gap in the mechanisms that previously reduced strategic uncertainty and thus reduce planners' and decision makers' reliance on incomplete intelligence and assumptions, rather than factual evidence.

Restrain, the last stabilising function, will face the largest challenges in the post-New START environment. Although New START imposed legally binding restrictions on the number of deployed strategic warheads and delivery systems, there were no restrictions placed upon modernisation programs, non-deployed stockpiles, or qualitative improvements to existing arsenals. After the treaty expired, both the United States and Russia possess the formal right to expand or diversify their nuclear forces without being bound by any

treaty restrictions. Thus, there exists a natural inclination to engage in behaviours that create uncertainty and can erode stability. The expansion of U.S. missile defence capabilities and Russia's development of systems such as the Burevestnik can be interpreted as forms of strategic hedging associated with the gradual erosion of restraint. Neither development necessarily implies an immediate return to a situation where nations will race to build up their respective nuclear arsenals numerically, but both indicate an increasing concern regarding the long-term durability of mutual limitations and second-strike assurances in a post-treaty environment. The development of U.S. missile defence capability has introduced concerns regarding possible future offensive-defensive imbalance issues. Similarly, Russia's development of novel delivery systems appears to be an attempt to protect against such potentialities. These two developments combined demonstrate how a decline in confidence in arms control agreements creates an incentive for nations to maintain deterrence using insurance capabilities, rather than by relying on reciprocal restraint.

The bilateral nature of New START also meant that the restraint imposed by the agreement applied only to the U.S.-Russian dyad; all other nuclear armed states were outside the bounds of its provisions (Pifer & Tyson, 2016). Given the current strategic environment, this absence of third-party constraints further reduces the likelihood of continued self-restraint (Wright, 2023). Absent legal obligation, restraint will depend almost entirely on voluntary adherence to norms, reputational concerns, or reciprocal signalling: mechanisms that are inherently weaker and more susceptible to political or security crises. As a result, the elimination of formal limits is likely to increase the incentive for expanding one's arsenal and engaging in hedging behaviour, which could produce increased uncertainty and encourage competitive behaviours that New START previously mitigated.

Conclusion

This article addressed the question to what extent the stabilising functions of bilateral arms control (predictability, transparency, and restraint) can remain after the expiration of New START. Drawing on strategic stability theory and a function-based analytical framework, the findings indicate that these functions are not equally resilient once formal institutional constraints are eliminated. While prior arms control agreements have decreased the security dilemma through reduced uncertainty and by moderating competitive behaviour, the expiration of New START has exposed the unequal resilience of the stabilising mechanisms institutionalised by those agreements.

From a theoretical standpoint, predictability is the least institutionally dependent stabilising function. Predictability, even in the absence of formal treaties, can be preserved to some degree by structural factors such as relatively stable force structures, enduring deterrence relations, and shared understandings of strategic parity. Such dynamics are consistent with realist theories that expect that when mutual vulnerability exists among states, there will continue to be incentives to

avoid destabilising arms races. However, such predictability is inherently less robust and more contingent than treaty-based predictability, since it lacks the formal ceilings, verification, and enforcement mechanisms that provide anchoring expectations over time.

By contrast, transparency and restraint are far more reliant on institutionalised cooperation. Strategic stability theory emphasises that transparency reduces the risk of misperception and worst-case planning by transforming private information into shared knowledge, while restraint depends on credible commitments that alter incentives for competitive expansion. Transparency could be partially maintained through voluntary data exchanges or confidence-building measures; restraint might be encouraged through reciprocal signalling or reputational incentives, for instance. However, the suspension of New START verification illustrated how quickly transparency is broken in the absence of binding rules, while ongoing modernisation, missile defence developments, and intensified nuclear signalling demonstrated how restraint erodes when institutional constraints weaken. In a self-help system characterised by heightened uncertainty, states increasingly favour hedging strategies that preserve flexibility over cooperative self-limitation.

The findings of this research therefore suggest that strategic stability in the absence of New START will be incomplete, fragile, and highly sensitive to political context. While bilateral arms control may be theoretically relevant as a means to manage the security dilemma, the ability of bilateral arms control to preserve the stabilising functions will depend upon both the design of institutions and the broader strategic context. Therefore, if comprehensive treaties do not exist, function-specific mechanisms such as voluntary data exchanges, informal confidence-building measures, reciprocal signalling, and reinforcement of normative expectations, may replace formally negotiated arms control in sustaining aspects of predictability, transparency, and restraint. However, such mechanisms will not possess the same level of durability and credibility as verification regimes established under legally binding treaties.

Ultimately, the expiration of New START underscores a central theoretical insight: strategic stability is not produced by treaties per se, but by the stabilising functions they embed within the strategic interaction of states. When those functions are no longer institutionalised, stability becomes increasingly dependent on informal practices, shared norms, and political will, making it more vulnerable to crisis and miscalculation. The opportunity now exists to move to a non-treaty stabilization mechanism: Moscow has offered to stay within the limits of New START for at least a year. If the United States agrees to start talks on the full range of factors affecting nuclear dangers, there will be a hope to maintain some strategic stability in a more complex and contested nuclear world.

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